

Colorimetric Estimation of Ce(IV) by Phenothiazines

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SANKH Gowda and others¹ have reported a method of estimation of Ce(IV) by using fluphenazine hydrochloride as a complexing reagent. Our present investigation relates to the use of different phenothiazines as reagents for the spectrophotometric estimation of Ce(IV).

Experimental

Standard solution of Ce(IV) (100 ppm) was prepared by dissolving requisite amount of ammonium ceric nitrate in distilled water and was standardised by the method given in literature². 1% solutions of phenothiazines in methanol were prepared and used as reagents.

Procedure : To a solution containing 100 μ g of cerium(IV) is added 0.5 ml of 1% ligand solution and mixed. The acidity of the mixture is adjusted between 2.4 to 4.0 molar with orthophosphoric acid in a total volume of 10 ml. The solution is diluted to 10 ml with distilled water and absorbance of the solution is recorded after 5 min at 510 nm. The amount of metal present in the solution is then determined from the calibration curve drawn under identical conditions.

The colour of the complex attains stability 5 min after the addition of reagent and is stable upto 25 min.

Physico chemical constants of the complexes have been summarised in Table I. Molar composition of the complexes were determined by Job's method of continuous variation³ and were found to be 1 : 1 (M : L) in all the cases.

TABLE I

Sl. No.	Reagent	Operative range from Ringbom's plot : μ g/ml	Molar absorptivity $\times 10^{-3}$ lit. mole ⁻¹ cm ⁻¹	Sandell's sensitivity μ g/cm ²
1.	Promethazine HCl	3.6 to 12.9	4.48	3.1×10^{-2}
2.	Pro-mazine HCl	5.6 to 12.9	5.61	2.5×10^{-2}
3.	Chlorpromazine	4.0 to 14.1	6.73	2.1×10^{-2}
4.	Thiopropazine mesylate	4.7 to 15.8	6.45	2.2×10^{-2}

The tolerance limits of various cations and anions are : Cd²⁺ (1 : 10); Ni²⁺ (1 : 8); Zr⁴⁺ (1 : 10); Cu²⁺ (1 : 10); Pb²⁺ (1 : 10); Fe²⁺ (1 : 10); U⁶⁺ (1 : 10); Mn²⁺ (1 : 10); Be²⁺ (1 : 10); Th⁴⁺ (1 : 10); Zn²⁺ (1 : 10); Ca²⁺ (1 : 10); Ba²⁺ (1 : 10); Cl⁻ (1 : 10); Br⁻ (1 : 10); SO₄²⁻ (1 : 10); NO₃⁻ (1 : 10); CH₃COO⁻ (1 : 10); ClO₄⁻ (1 : 8); B₄O₇²⁻ (1 : 10); MoO₄²⁻ (1 : 6); C₂O₄²⁻ (1 : 10).

It was found that cations such as Sn²⁺, Fe²⁺, As³⁺, V⁵⁺ and anions such as NO₂⁻, Fe(CN)₆⁴⁻, CNS⁻, S₂O₈²⁻, SO₃²⁻, BrO₃⁻ interfere seriously with the reaction.

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Spectrophotometric Determination of Ruthenium with Prochlorperazine Bismethanesulphonate

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DURING the investigation on the reaction of phenothiazines with metal ions, prochlorperazine bismethanesulphonate, (PCPMS) 2-chloro-10-[3-(4-methyl-1-piperiziny) propyl] phenothiazine bismethanesulphonate, was found to give red colour with ruthenium(III) in phosphoric, sulphuric or hydrochloric acid. This reaction is now utilized for rapid spectrophotometric determination of ruthenium(III). The proposed method offers the advantages of simplicity, rapidity, sensitivity, reasonable selectivity and determination at room temperature without the need for extraction.

Experimental

Reagents and apparatus : A stock solution of ruthenium(III) was prepared by dissolving ruthenium(III) chloride (Johnson and Matthey, London) in dilute hydrochloric acid and diluting to 1 litre to give a solution of 1 M with respect to hydrochloric acid. The solution was standardized gravimetrically¹ and was further diluted to give a solution of 25 μ g/ml. A 0.2% solution of PCPMS was prepared in double distilled water and stored in an amber bottle in a refrigerator. A Beckman Model DB spectrophotometer with matched 1 cm silica cells was used for absorbance measurements.

Procedure : An aliquot of the stock solution containing 5-205 μ g of ruthenium(III) and 14 ml of 10 M phosphoric acid were transferred to a 25 ml volumetric flask, 3 ml of 0.2% PCPMS solution was added to this and the volume made upto the mark with double distilled water. The solutions were